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Catasema vulpina flavovulpina ssp. n. (Lepidoptera, Noctuidae) from Uzbekistan

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Abstract. Description of *Catasema vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n. from Uzbekistan with 10 colour illustrations and 6 genitalia figures.

Keywords. Uzbekistan, taxonomy, Noctuidae, new description.

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Introduction

The author of this article studied a short series of specimens resembling *Catasema vulpina* (Staudinger, 1888) in external features, but with yellow wings, from an isolated population from the western edge of the Chatkal range in northeastern Uzbekistan. The male and female genitalia structure resemble those of the specimens of the nominotypical *C. vulpina*, but the author found differences in genital structure in addition to the conspicuous external features. Thus, it is recognized and described as a new subspecies here below.

Taxonomic account

Catasema Staudinger, 1888 is a monotypic genus of the family Noctuidae, tribe *Episemini* Guenée, 1837 (Fibiger & Lafontaine 2005; Fibiger & Hacker 2005). However, the taxonomic interpretation of *Episemini* needs further discussion; Hacker (1991) assigned it to *Ipimorphinae*. Since the larvae exhibit *Hadeninae* features (Beck, 1999) and on this basis Ronkay, Yela & Hreblay (2001) placed it as being at the end of *Hadeninae*. The latest assignation is the subfamily *Xyleninae* Guenée, 1837 (Fibiger & Lafontaine 2005; Fibiger & Hacker 2005).

The type species (and the only species) of the genus is *Catasema vulpina* (Staudinger, 1888), which was associated theoretically to the genus *Episema* Ochsenheimer, 1816 as *Episema vulpina* Staudinger, 1888 in the original description. However, Staudinger subsequently assigned it to *Catasema*, a genus he erected in the same year. *C. vulpina* is a local Central Asiatic species; the type locality is near Margelan, in the southeastern extension of Uzbekistan, close to the borders of Kirgisia and Tajikistan. It occurs in Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kirgisia, and Tajikistan between altitudes 1400 and 2800 meters and seems the most common in the Hissar Mountains of Tajikistan. The flight period is the second half of September and October.

Abbreviations for personal and institutional collections used herein: PGM = collection of Péter Gyulai (Miskolc, Hungary); GYP = genitalia slide Péter Gyulai; m = male; f = female; HT = holotype; PT = paratype.

Description of new taxon***Catasema vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n. (Figs 9–12, 14, 17, 18)**

Holotype: male, Uzbekistan, Chimgan, 1600 m, 20. IX. 1992, leg. L. Misko, GYP 5802 (coll. P. Gyulai, Miskolc, Hungary)

Paratypes: 1 m, 2 f, with the same data (PGM); slide nos. GYP 5806m, GYP 5803f

Diagnosis. *Catasema vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n. (Figs 9–12) differs from *C. vulpina* by the pale yellowish wings and the regressed, obscure wing pattern, with the exception of the brown, conspicuous postmedial line in the forewings and the median line in the hindwings. Pale orange ground coloured specimens with somewhat obscure wing pattern can be also found among *C. vulpina*, but *C. vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n. can be easily separated from them by the monocolours yellowish wings and the conspicuous, sharp median line in the hindwing.

Description (Figs 9–12). Forewing length 13–15 mm, wingspan 27–32 mm. Vesture of head, thorax, abdomen, and forewings pale yellowish, the hindwings slightly lighter. Wing patterns absent or obscure, with the exception of the brown, fine, zig-zag antemedial line and the conspicuous postmedial line in the forewings and the slightly less sharp median line in the hindwings. Orbicular and reniform stigmata absent or hardly guessed, the same colour as the ground. Claviform stigma not indicated.

Male genitalia (Figs 17–18). The structure of *C. vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n. male genital organ is basically the same as that of *C. vulpina*. The main features are the moderately long and slightly spatulate uncus; shield-shaped juxta with long dorsal medial extension with bilateral appendages terminally; elongate, evenly curved, almost equally wide valva with broad corona; strong, finger-like, slightly curved harpe. Aedeagus tubular, long. Vesica curved ventrad, tubular, bearing two small basal cornuti with rounded base and tiny tip; a strong wedge shaped medial cornutus without broader base and a faint, slight sclerotized line subterminally.

Female genitalia. (Fig. 14). Papillae anales setose, broad, angular; apophyses anteriores and posteriores thin, the latter ones longer. Ostium oval, antrum broadly funnel-like, strongly sclerotized. Ductus bursae short, asymmetrically strongly sclerotized, medially asymmetrically constricted, longitudinally wrinkled. Appendix bursae and corpus bursae large, saccate, the former much larger, curved posteriorly with a few longitudinal wrinkles.

Biology and distribution. The new subspecies is known from the type locality only in the western edge of the Chatkal range, at moderately high altitude (1600 m), in northeaster Uzbekistan.

Etymology. The name of the new subspecies is a combination of the name of the nomenclotypical subspecies and the pale yellowish wings of the new subspecies.

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Figures 1–8. *Catasema* spp. adults. 1–2. *C. vulpina*, m, Cotype, Usbekistan, Margelan, coll. MFN Berlin, B 156; 3–4. *C. vulpina*, f, Cotype, Usbekistan, Margelan, coll. MFN Berlin; 5. *C. vulpina*, m, Kyrgyzstan, Naryn reg., GYP 5801, coll. Gyulai; 6. *C. vulpina*, m, Tajikistan, Hissar Mts., Maichura, coll. Gyulai; 7. *C. vulpina*, f, Tajikistan, Hissar Mts., Gushary, GYP 5804, coll. Gyulai; 8. *C. vulpina*, f, Tajikistan, Hissar Mts., Gushary, coll. Gyulai

Figures 9–14. *Catasema* sp. and ssp. n. adults and female genitalia. 9. *C. vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n., m, HT, Uzbekistan, Chimgan, coll. Gyulai, GYP 5802; 10. *C. vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n., m, PT, Uzbekistan, Chimgan, coll. Gyulai, GYP 5806; 11. *C. vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n., f, PT, Uzbekistan, Chimgan, coll. Gyulai; 12. *C. vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n., f, PT, Uzbekistan, Chimgan, coll. Gyulai, GYP 5803; 13. *C. vulpina*, Tajikistan, Hissar Mts., GYP 5804; 14. *C. vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n., PT, Uzbekistan, Chimgan, GYP 5803

Figures 15–18. *Catasema* sp. and ssp. n. male genitalia. 15. *C. vulpina*, Cotypte, Uzbekistan, Margelan, coll. MFN Berlin, 156; 16. *C. vulpina*, Kyrgyzstan, Naryn reg., coll. Gyulai, GYP 5801; 17. *C. vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n., HT, Uzbekistan, Chimgan, coll. Gyulai, GYP 5802; 18. *C. vulpina flavovulpina* ssp. n., PT, Uzbekistan, Chimgan, coll. Gyulai, GYP 5806.

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